

Score-level Sample Size Requirements for Technology-enhanced Items: A Simulation Study

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Abstract

The use of technology-enhanced items (TEIs) brings great possibilities for item development and item scoring. This study explores the impact of insufficient score-level sample size on item characteristics and data-model for TEIs that can be better interpreted by polytomous scoring with the use of partial credit model.

Research Question

The use of technology enhanced items (TEIs) opens a new area for psychometrics in that most item types portend to multiple correct actions or answer keys moving us to go beyond simple right/wrong responses towards polytomous scoring. Unlike dichotomous items, here exists a special consideration regarding whether all score categories would have enough sample sizes to sustain accurate model calibration. Earlier research (Betts & Kim, 2014; Betts, Kim, & Muntean, 2015; Betts, Wolf, Muntean, & Kim, 2016; DeMars, 2003; He & Wheadon, 2013; Wang & Chen, 2005) has focused on the sample size requirements at the item level. This study investigated how sample size on the score level affects the stability and accuracy of the Partial Credit Model (PCM; Masters, 1982) parameters.

Research Design

❖ Model

In the PCM, $P(\theta, x)$ is the probability of a person j with ability θ , whose score x on a polytomous item i with a maximum score m :

$$P(\theta_j, x_i) = \frac{\exp \sum_{k=0}^x (\theta_j - \delta_{ik})}{\sum_{r=0}^m \exp \sum_{k=0}^r (\theta_j - \delta_{ik})}$$

This study uses the Rasch PCM with Andrich threshold:

$$P(\theta_j, x_i) = \frac{\exp \sum_{k=0}^x (\theta_j - D_i - F_{ik})}{\sum_{r=0}^m \exp \sum_{k=0}^r (\theta_j - D_i - F_{ik})}$$

where D_i is the average item difficulty of item i , and F_{ik} is the Rasch-Andrich thresholds, which are usually ascending and sum to zero across all the categories.

❖ Simulation factor- item

- Step distance ($k_j - k_{j-1}$): 2.5, 2, 1.5, 1, 0.5
- Average item difficulty (D_j): -1, -0.5, 0, 0.5, 1
- Score category (k):
3-point item: (0, 1, 2)
4-point item: (0, 1, 2, 3)
5-point item: (0, 1, 2, 3, 4)
- Item design: 5*5*3=75

Mean difficulty	Andrich threshold				Step distance
	1	2	3	4	
-1	-3.75	-1.25	1.25	3.75	2.5
-1	-3.5	-1	1	3.5	2
-1	-1.25	-0.75	0.75	1.25	1.5
-1	-1.5	-0.5	0.5	1.5	1
-1	-0.75	-0.25	0.25	0.75	0.5
-0.5	-3.75	-1.25	1.25	3.75	2.5
-0.5	-3.5	-1	1	3.5	2
-0.5	-1.25	-0.75	0.75	1.25	1.5
-0.5	-1.5	-0.5	0.5	1.5	1
-0.5	-0.75	-0.25	0.25	0.75	0.5
MORE...

❖ Simulation factor- person

- 20000 examinees $\sim N(0,1)$
- Score-level sample size (s): 200, 100, 50, 25, 12, 6, 3, 0
- Score-level sample size design:
3-point item: 3*8
4-point item: 4*8
5-point item: 5*8
- 100 replications

sample size	0	1	2	missing	Total
All	1891	9643	8466	0	20000
score_2_S1	1891	9643	200	8266	20000
score_2_S2	1891	9643	100	8366	20000
score_2_S3	1891	9643	50	8416	20000
score_2_S4	1891	9643	25	8441	20000
score_2_S5	1891	9643	12	8454	20000
score_2_S6	1891	9643	6	8460	20000
score_2_S7	1891	9643	3	8463	20000
score_2_S8	1891	9643	0	8466	20000

❖ Calibration method

Unanchored, person-anchored, and item-anchored calibrations in Winsteps (Linacre, 2005).

❖ Evaluation criteria

The calibration results from the complete, simulated data were used as the benchmark for comparison. The evaluation criteria include average item difficulty (D_j), model-data-fit, and the displacement index from the item-anchored calibrations

Results and Discussion

model-data-fit

All simulated cases show good unstandardized infit and outfit statistics regardless the level of sample size on each score point.

Percent of disordered thresholds

The zero-score point has 0% disordered threshold when the sample size is greater than 0; The middle score categories have 100% disordered threshold when the score level sample size is 200 or less.

Average item difficulty (D_j)

3-point item (score= 0, 1, 2)

4-point item (score= 0, 1, 2, 3)

5-point item (score= 0, 1, 2, 3, 4)

1. Person-anchored calibration results are consistent with the unanchored results.

2. The average item difficulty seems to be functionally related to the same size of the lowest and highest score points.

3. For score zero, the smaller the sample size is, the easier the item becomes. Items become easier as the threshold difference becomes small. With no responses, the same item looks more difficult than the true.

4. For the highest score point, The smaller the sample size is, the harder the item becomes. Items become harder as the threshold difference becomes small. With no responses, the same item looks a lot easier than the true value.

5. The impact of score-level sample size on the average difficult becomes less severe as the number of score points increases.

6. The middle score categories are not sensitive to different sample sizes.

7. The displacement values from the item anchored calibration show that as the number of score points increases, the effect of parameter drift is less severe.

Conclusions

The development of TEIs aids to improve the validity and fidelity of a test. It is concerning that little studies can be found for investing the effect of score-level sample size on parameter recovery and the implications of not having enough responses to fully represent a score group.

This simulation study found that the small/missing sample size on the score level won't affect the model-data-fit. The average item difficulty is functionally related to the same size of the lowest and highest score points. It is also related to the size of the step difference. As the number of score category increases, the impact of sample size on the average difficulty becomes less severe. Even though the small sample size of middle score categories won't affect the average difficulty, it caused high percentage of disordered thresholds.

This study concludes that the use of PCM model requires enough sample size for the lowest and highest score points. Understanding the score-level sample size requirements of PCM should help testing practitioners design their field testing and define the level of stability and accuracy of model parameters.

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